

Philosophy and Practice of Science: A Critique

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Abstract

The implication of scientific methodology in terms of its philosophical roots and divergences constitutes a massive untapped topic for modern academics. This paper's critical review articulates the philosophical premises of positivism and constructivism, which eventually define scientific approaches with their respective limitations. It also extends the discussion of the issues and concerns inherent when applying these frameworks in pragmatic empirical studies, as highlighted by post-positivists, including tensions between theory and implementation. It reviews the literature to understand how ethical issues and methodological stringency hinder the assimilation of philosophical critique into scientific practice. The dichotomy between natural science and social science is becoming thinner, and they are now moving toward a continuum approach to contributing to each other. The paper concludes that the philosophy and practices of science have become complex and a political tool that dilutes it from the beauty of metaphysics and eventually leads to a hegemonic regime of politics. Thus, this paper calls for a more dialogical philosophy on science and scientific methods.

Keywords: science, philosophy, metaphysics, knowledge, research methods, criticism

Introduction

The metaphysics of science, a central concern in the philosophy of science, grapples with the questions of how science functions and whether such an investigation is appropriate. At its heart, it scrutinizes the axioms that govern the creation, validation, and refutation of scientific knowledge. Knowledge is not necessarily real and permanent; factual and evidence-based knowledge can only form science. In this context, Aripova (2022) argues that philosophy is a bridging platform or functional unity of scientific and non-scientific knowledge. The sociological perspective on scientific knowledge, as expounded by eminent philosophers such as Karl Popper, Thomas Kuhn, and Paul Feyerabend, compels us to question the objectivity and structure of the scientific method (Popper, 2005; Kuhn, 1962; Feyerabend, 2010). It is also important to note that, as is often the case in such discussions, there is a significant focus on the contrast between the idealized scientific models that present science as an 'objective' and 'methodological' field, and the actual practice of science in the often mundane and ethically ambiguous real world..

The scientific method conceives a disciplinary integrity, sometimes allowing a continuum between the natural and social sciences. However, this distinction has its theoretical problems, which further invite empirical dilemmas such as the collection and analysis of data, scientific theorization, and validation of the concluding reality. Does science answer everything? Is it perfect? What was before science, and what will be after it? Is this world knowable ideally by science or just partially? Many philosophical underpinnings are vital in science studies and disciplines, involving the approach to research and the analysis of outcomes (McNabb, 2015). For example, positivism, characteristic of many works of the natural sciences, is oriented on

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the empirical observation of facts and follows the principles of objectification. On the other hand, the interpretivist and constructivist paradigms effectively employed in the social sciences are focused on the ways that different people might interpret social phenomena (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020; Matthews, 2024).

This paper seeks to critically examine the paradigms of philosophy in light of the practice of science and the ethical and methodological implications that arise from that place. The primary focus is on the relationship between philosophy and science, particularly in ontological positions, theoretical roots, empirical contestations, and critique of the science. The paper underlines the pressing need for an integrated approach to a more philosophically informed science, highlighting the urgency and importance of the topic. It remains unexplained how this can be attained even though there is consensus about its necessity. The central questions of science are three-dimensional: what to know, why to know, and how to know. If a verified source of knowledge logically addresses these questions, it turns into science. As articulated in *vijñāna*, science is knowing the matter 'as it is', i.e. *Yathā-bhūta-ñāna-dassana*. This is also conceptualized as the transaction of knowledge (*jñāna or gyān*) and cognition (*saṃjñāna*) in Indian philosophical traditions. Under these circumstances, how can new ways be innovative for elucidating the philosophical and methodological issues about applying those concepts in science? Therefore, the paper attempts to answer the contested question of how philosophical paradigms influence current scientific practices.

Methods

This paper adopts the systematic review approach of reviewing the relevant literature on the philosophy of science and its criticisms. The primary purpose of this approach is to examine and contrast philosophical paradigms of science concerning present-day practices and developments in scientific methodology, a topic of significant interest and engagement. Critical philosophical works by Karl Popper, Thomas Kuhn, and Paul Feyerabend are discussed to build the intellectual groundwork for their critique of science. The paper critically outlines historical perspectives and scientific movements. Furthermore, critiques of scientific methods and the ethicality of current scientific practice proposed in the recent literature are considered to identify the current state of the practice (Friedman, 2015; Kidd, 2015).

By employing this review-based synthesis method, we can gain a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between philosophy and science, thereby enhancing our knowledge and enlightenment in these fields. In this regard, the methodology includes three primary steps:

1. **Literature Review:** A review of original works by prominent philosophers of science and secondary works dealing with the philosophy of science and ethics in research practices.
2. **Synthesis:** The integration of mainstream paradigms and critical issues of science interacting with the research methodologies in the natural and the social world.
3. **Analysis:** A bibliographical outline of the impact of the gap between philosophy and practice on ethical and methodological practice in scientific research.

Results

Metaphysics and Science

Metaphysics, a branch of philosophy, explores questions relating to reality, existence, and the nature of being or relationships between objects, properties, and events on an abstract level. It is concerned with such mysterious (sometimes abstract, non-empirical) questions as the nature of being itself, including what time entails and whether it would continue if reality were not in space anymore. Metaphysics entails some fundamental characteristic properties, including ontological questions (what is reality and does it exist), epistemological questions (what is the method of knowing reality), and methodological questions (the tools to verify and examine the causal conditions underlying physicality and socially constructed world). Metaphysics seeks to make sense of the fundamental principles that underlie these abstract concepts and, as such, presents a view that is not in contrast but rather complementary to science, which is primarily based on empirical validation of observable evidence.

In its simplest form, the term 'metaphysics' derives from the two words of the ancient Greek language: *metá* (μετά, meaning 'after', 'over', and 'above') and *phusiká* (φυσικά) with the original name of this branch of science being *ta metá ta phusiká*, that is, 'after the physical'. Indeed, a metaphysical question is not only about the happening or being of any event presently existing now, but also before (what was) and after (what will). It is also about the science of 'non-existing' and whether there is anything in the world. In the same way, the word science was borrowed from the Anglo-Norman language as the suffix '-cience', which was borrowed from the Latin word '*scientia*'. It denotes knowledge of a particular world phenomenon (to know, to be aware, and to understand). Nevertheless, knowing the things to their exact existence is the most complicated question in science and scientific methodology.

Van Inwagen (2024) articulates metaphysics as the exploration of fundamental questions about existence, causality, and reality, challenging the assumptions of 'whatever is'. Loux (2017) significantly contributes to this ongoing discourse, offering a fresh perspective on metaphysical concerns related to the existence of things and the nature of existence. Their works underscore the crucial role of a thoughtful, in-depth study in comprehending the complex and profound metaphysical concepts that underpin various philosophical essays in ancient and contemporary traditions. In the eastern Vedanta perspective, metaphysics is a comprehensive assessment of reality's existence at both macro and micro levels. It reveals that there is nothing beyond existence; even non-existence also exists. Nothing is 'larger or bigger' than metaphysical elongation or extraction remains, and nothing remains 'smaller' than its contraction. Therefore, it originates before the beginning, continues in the meantime, and goes after the ending. It indicates a minor demarcation line between wholeness and emptiness, which are complementary and not metaphysically contradictory, reflecting that 'this is that' and 'that is this'.

On the other hand, science is a systematic method of acquiring knowledge and constructing theories and laws for describing (and predicting) natural phenomena (Chalmers, 2013). Science is a process based on observation, experimentation, and empirical reasoning to develop a reliable understanding of the principles of repeatability and verifiability of the methods employed (Popper, 2002). While science and metaphysics both seek to understand reality, they do so in distinct ways. Science, rooted in empiricism, is the result of honest-to-goodness perceptual investigation. Metaphysics, on the other hand, deals with fundamental questions regarding being and quintessence beyond our senses. These two fields, seemingly disparate, actually offer a holistic view of what there is in the world and how it works, revealing an intricate interconnectedness that is intellectually stimulating.

In Eastern Hindu philosophical traditions, metaphysics is considered the root of science. The meaning associated with the notion of science differs from one school of thought to the other within different *Āstika* (orthodoxy, which includes schools that accept the authority of the Vedas) and *Nāstika* (heterodoxy, which includes schools that do not accept the authority of the Vedas) traditions. The Vedanta school of science focuses on the self (*Ātman*) and how it relates to the supreme reality (*Brahman*). There is nothing that remains to know when the science of reality is known (*Para-Brahman*), going beyond all kinds of illusions (*Māyā*) and ignorance (*Avidyā*). However, the Vedanta perspective also offers various methods to observe the science (the wholeness, i.e. non-duality or *Advaita*, and the divisibility, i.e. duality or *Dvaita*).

Conversely, Buddhism defines science as an inquiry into *Anattā* —the notion of no-self, a fundamental concept in Buddhism that refers to the absence of a permanent, unchanging entity within a person. This concept is central to Buddhist philosophy and has profound implications for the understanding of science. Much is stressed on impermanency and the absence of being or self. It is articulated with the cause-effect analysis, defined as the principle of dependent origination, i.e. *Pratītyasamutpāda*. At the same time, Jain philosophy views science as the way of seeing the truth under the doctrine of *Anekāntavāda*. It stands for non-absolutism of phenomena, as scientific assessment can be made through multiplicity and the multifaceted nature of truth.

In their unique way, Chinese philosophical traditions conceptualize science and its role in shaping social values and norms. In Confucianism, science is not just theoretical knowledge, but the practical knowledge of morality and social organization, in harmony with the universe's concept of balance and order, known as harmony. For Leydesdorff (2021), knowledge is produced discursively. This harmony encompasses ethical conduct and the principles of nature, enlightening us about the practical application of science in our daily lives. Similarly, Taoism views science as understanding the elemental process (*Tao*) and the essential forces (*Yin* and *Yang*) in alignment with the natural course of existence, favoring intuition over logic. This comparison reveals the distinct views of Chinese and Indian philosophical frameworks on the nature and purpose of science. However, both uphold emancipatory worldviews and assert that science is rooted in the liberation and empowerment of humanity.

Debating ‘Positivism’ against ‘Constructivism’

Positivism has long been established as one of the dominant philosophies and is primarily used as a fundamental methodological approach in different disciplines of natural sciences. The root of positivism in quantitative research is the idea that knowledge must be based on factual, tangible information (Kellstedt & Whitten, 2018). This perspective holds that science is an objective form of wisdom that rigorously adheres to rigorous, step-by-step methodological procedures to guarantee reproducibility. Positivism has been highly beneficial in areas like physics, chemistry, etc., where proof, tests/experiments, and collection of facts and data are essential to discover (Hay, 2014; Hutten, 2022). In earlier times, positivism was championed in social science by Auguste Comte, John Stuart Mill, Émile Durkheim, and Herbert Spencer. However, it became popular and was followed by many social theorists. Positivism often emphasizes empirical science by rejecting metaphysical speculation. It advocates for a systematic, observational approach to understanding both natural and social phenomena. The central theme of positivism relies on objectivism, which articulates that the world is objective, quantified, and measurable.

Social science is the scientific delineation of society and social realities, which are primarily subjective and interpretive. However, some critical issues exist in using positivism in social

science. Social trends are multifaceted, and many processes demonstrate subjective, culturally specific historical content that is difficult to measure (Creswell & Creswell, 2022). Positivism relies on empirical facts, which may reduce subjective observations by failing to capture the hermeneutic nature of people's actions and proficiency in social relations and their meanings. Indeed, the focus on numbers and facts is helpful, though the validity of the reality cannot be only judged by the 'numerical evidence'. Moreover, it tends to lead us more toward the quantitative at the expense of some essential qualitative elements that might be difficult to quantify but remain critical — though again, often neglected to explore the nature of subjective realities of the material world (Hay, 2014).

Critics have also argued that positivism results in excessive methodological regulation or rigidity of scientific inquiries. This assumption is problematic as it implies that all scientific endeavours should be reducible to empiricism universally in exact terms. Reductionism is the most fundamental critique of positivism, which relies on the critique of derivatives of the metaphysical elements of the things or reach problems that we observe and investigate. Subjective characteristics of worldly events, such as feelings, experiences, perceptions, and attitudes, cannot be judged and measured precisely in the 'weighing machines or numeric quartiles' by the positivist approaches due to their volatility and ever-changing dynamics. Taking this critique, the post-positivist paradigm claims that the objective world is probably actual but not 'absolute and permanent' as the positivist often claims. For the post-positivists, objective realities are probabilistic and skeptical.

Contrarily to the positivist and post-positivist ontology of science, constructivism is centred on analyzing social events from the outlook or worldview of people in terms of their engagement with the events of the subjective world (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020). For constructivists, reality is not a single and absolute notion; it is constantly changing and developing in multiple and diverse ways. This paradigm is commonly employed in the social sciences, where researchers can examine how people, individually or in groups, make and give meaning to those experiences they encounter in social settings. It puts a premium on the construction of knowing and acknowledges that fact is always socially realized, constructed, reconstructed, and deconstructed. Reality is subject to interpretation, explanation, and constructive articulation. Therefore, the constructivist approach is also popularly known as 'interpretivism', which emphasizes the importance of understanding how individuals interpret and give meaning to their experiences. To put it further, the real meaning of the things or events that we investigate lies in how we observe, interpret, and theorize them, irrespective of the objective conditions of the event itself. Hence, realities are not things but are mental constructions, and interpretations manifested diversely and differently.

As mentioned earlier, constructivism excels in evaluating subjective reality but also grapples with the challenge of measuring and assessing it in scientific terms. When discussing the criticisms of the constructivist approach, one common observation is that the findings often lack generalizability. Since interpretivist research tends to limit the sample size and localize the research contexts, such findings cannot be easily generalized (Friedman, 2015). Furthermore, constructivists and interpretivists are prone to biases, making the researcher's prejudices, choices, preferences, negligence, ignorance, expertise, likes, and dislikes a significant concern. Unlike the participants, the observers or researchers may inadvertently inject their views when attempting to uncover and compare consistencies and differences in the views held by the participants; the process is not entirely objective.

Constructivism in scientific research is applicable where the nature of research questions is subjective or difficult to quantify. However, it may encounter several issues and criticisms. The validity of the multi-real world, the data's trustworthiness, and the researcher's and research participants' biases are critical elements in this regard. Constructivism may lack objective rigour, eventually leading to the problem of generalizing the research findings. There is a definite pull toward quantitative empiricism in many academic disciplines and, most sharply, in the sciences. Quantitative empiricism refers to the emphasis on measurable and quantifiable data in research. Thus, the constructivist paradigm and interpretive approaches may be underestimated or excluded, and qualitative research questions, which social scientists may be interested in, will remain beyond reach.

Integration of Philosophical and Scientific Practices

Philosophy and scientific practices have been rarely discussed in the relational approach. While the philosophical approach is metaphysically abstract, science tends to be more concrete, distinct, and specific. Despite the insight that philosophical critiques bring into how science works, applying knowledge from such critiques is usually severely restricted by institutional procedures and methodological confines. For example, while some philosophical radicals about science, such as Feyerabend, who supports relativism, mean methodology in which there are numerous scientific methods, what is witnessed today is a more standardized abstract and rational approach to science. This approach often prioritizes quantifiable data and follows a linear, step-by-step process (Kusch, 2020; Feyerabend, 2010).

However, there is always a gap between the principles of science and the principles of scientific investigation. For instance, whereas philosophers advanced methodological concerns, researchers have to undergo a lot of pressure and rigidity in terms of reproducibility and objectivity (Friedman, 2015; Kidd, 2015). These institutional and methodological restrictions complicate research activities and do not allow for the construction of complex integrative links between philosophical reflections, scientific activities, and knowledge systems. According to Popper (2013), scientific knowledge is geared toward realism, that science seeks not merely a way to reach out to the world but rather how the world genuinely is. On the other hand, Hanson (2014) even raised the issue of whether scientific discovery has one touchstone at all, arguing that discovery may depend on various reasoning processes other than objective ones. This ongoing discussion, which remains relevant and timely, eventually creates scientific knowledge and innovation contestation.

Science is a significant and manifold element of social life that impacts the perception of this world and the prognosis of its development, promotion of new technologies, and solution of various problems related to human life. Science, as a study or analysis of the nature and development of the physical universe by a scientific method, observation, and experimentation of natural phenomena, has contributed to real growth, especially in sectors including medicine and engineering, as well as the ever-growing concern on environmental conservation. Beyond its specific findings, science provides societies with a means for making practical choices – it enables us to address the world's problems today: global warming, diseases, and poverty. Moreover, science creates future opportunities for the innovative development of new technologies and industries that will improve the economy. This stress on the potential of science to improve the economy can help the audience feel reassured and confident in the role of science in driving economic progress and prosperity.

The tangled web of how science and our socio-political existence interact has been woven into the fabric around modern living. As government activities and the scientific community converge, it is evident that the contemporary world system is not merely a regulative apparatus

but also a formative structure of science-inspired originality responding to social demand. This view challenged the orthodoxy that the bourgeois state and capitalism are distinct entities (Carroll, 2015). Further, there is evidence of the integration of science within legal systems and where it is required that the development of technology respects the ethics and rights of human beings. As debate intensifies over bio-technologies, especially genetic engineering, the law needs to transition from mechanical normative rules into cognitive gaps that need to be normalized publicly by employing adaptive tools (Greco & Santosuosso, 2004). It also highlights science as an engine of moving forward and helping for shared values, showing that the interface between scientific discovery and social direction is propitious and necessary.

Historical Perspectives on Scientific Critique

A critique of science from a historical perspective has matured into a contemporary form from the early philosophical questions raised by Plato and Aristoteles. The empirical approach was introduced by scholars of the Renaissance and Enlightenment practices like Galileo and Newton; philosophers like David Hume and Immanuel Kant provided skeptical accounts of empirical conclusions. The nineteenth-century positivism came into practice through Auguste Comte. However, in the 20th century, Karl Popper and Thomas Kuhn responded by demanding falsifiability, a concept that suggests a scientific theory must be potentially disprovable by evidence. Falsifiability is a key principle in the philosophy of science, stating that for a hypothesis to be considered scientific, it must be possible to design an experiment that could potentially prove it false. They also advocated for changing theories with scientific paradigms, which can invite a revolution in socio-political change. The scholars, particularly those who belong to schools of critical theory view, deepened criticism of their position, presented with feminist and postcolonial perspectives, calling attention to power, culture, and ideology in constructing the scientific (Matthews, 2024). Such a sequence indicates the increasing appreciation of the socio-political aspects of science eroding the principle of its neutrality and general applicability.

It was suggested above that the historical development of scientific critique was predisposed to deriving epistemological change, each time altering how the knowledge power interface was cast. The dominant paradigm in society might be scientifically grounded and conditioned as we perceive it. However, the socio-cultural and political factors that are part of the practices of the scientific process for social change and political revolutions have been largely neglected in the history of science. On the other hand, the social science paradigm also romanticizes the inability of socio-cultural and political-economic factors rather than navigating scientific inventions, technological development, and new modes of production. Therefore, contemporary scholars rightly argue that diversity and variability in phenomena like monumentality, megalithic construction, etc., provide reasons to integrate with local perspectives and ethno-archaeological insights for scientific narratives. Local perspectives refer to the unique viewpoints and knowledge systems of specific communities, while ethno-archaeological insights are interpretations of archaeological data from the perspective of the people who produced it. These elements enrich scientific narratives by providing a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under study (Wunderlich et al., 2019). Social norms and values are embedded in society, while social science aims to shape generalizable scientific takeaways from community contexts. Second, a theoretical framework known as 'transcendental pragmatics in dialogue with hermeneutics' supports critically examining the normative assumptions guiding scientific work. This framework, which combines transcendental philosophy with the study of interpretation, can help scholars overcome the relativistic tendencies in traditional hermeneutical thought by articulating meta-normative conditions for critique—for example, symmetry and reciprocity (Hedberg, 2004). This

exemplifies a previously discussed concept, but I reiterate the dynamic nature of scientific critique, which promotes objectivity and inclusivity in science.

Key Philosophical Movements Challenging Scientific Authority

Three critical philosophical trends have conflicted with science by casting doubt on the scientific narratives of objectivity and assertiveness. Enlightenment rationalism and its positivist school of thought experienced a scientific crisis beginning in the 19th century. This crisis became apparent in the post-World War II era, along with the appearance of Karl Popper and Danial Little. Popper's theory of falsification, in particular, rejected the possibility of verifying theories instead of holding on to the possibility of falsifying them. Thomas Kuhn first came up with the idea of shifts in the paradigms through which, alone, science could be viewed as a thing that advances in a straight, linear line (Kuhn, 1962, 2022). The 1960s and 1970s, a time of deep modernism, saw the emergence of a significant philosophical debate (Hodge & Cantor, 2020; Weyl, 2021).

While modernists champion the authority of science and its factual basis, postmodernists adopt a more critical stance, questioning the purity, authority, and dominance of what is commonly referred to as science. By rejecting grand theory, postmodernism criticizes the possibility of scientific objectivity, asserts epistemological relativity in societal and cultural contexts, and maintains that science is embedded with language, politics, power, and ideology. Postmodernism contributed to the advancement of constructivism, which further increased the debate and dismissed scientific knowledge as a socially constructed and politically and historically contingent activity. Indeed, postmodernism is a collective movement manifested in different sectors of public life, ideology, politics, science, and literature. For example, postmodern feminisms, voiced by Donna Haraway and Sandra Harding, unveiled the profiling of feminist bias in the methods by which scientific knowledge was produced and insisted on the revolutionary improvement of cognition, inspiring potential for change. For them, science and technology are more androcentric, and it has been a tool for women's subordination. Postmodernism, with its potential for transformative change, inspires us to rethink the status quo and strive for a more inclusive and diverse scientific community.

There have been and still are to this day philosophical movements that, throughout history, arose to question the unquestioned authority of science. For example, postmodernism's legitimacy is questioned for its powerful critique of modern science's pursuit of objectivity and preference over socially rendered knowledge. As McNeish, 2017 (p. 3) asserts in highlighting the tensions between radical and mainstream currents within green politics, the political framing of scientific data can also be seen. Elsewhere, feminist epistemology has criticized the marginalized male bias characteristic of significant streams in scientific discourse and, for novelty, a better understanding of knowledge that accounts for different lived experiences. This also goes for the so-called universality claimed in and by much scientific discourse, which can often obscure rather than give justice to marginalized voices. Like critical theory, it questions the interplay of knowledge production and power: Who gets to count as a knowledgeable member of society? These movements together make a compelling case for democratic knowledge, emphasizing the urgent need to challenge the authority of science and strive for a more inclusive and diverse scientific community.

Current concerns in scientific work are primarily centred on ethical conduct, reporting and replication, and concerns over the usage of scientific discoveries. The evolving landscape of contemporary scientific practice prompts critical reflection on underlying epistemological frameworks and methodologies. Increasingly, scholars are examining the implications of

Kant's philosophy, particularly how his concepts of teleology (the study of the purpose or design of natural phenomena) and function (the role or purpose of a biological structure or process) resonate with modern approaches to biology and the cognitive processes involved in scientific inquiry (Portera & Šustar, 2015). This link addresses a significant break from the view of science as divorced from cognitive involvement and independent of how humans seek to grasp; this distinction shows that making knowledge acts not just as intersubjective verification but also as affairs made possible through human thought processes. In addition, design and critical practice play a crucial role in how we might problematize both technologically in terms of what is considered good design (around particular forms of expertise?) within the development sphere by requiring a reflexive engagement with practices (Mazé et al., 2007). These practices encourage a more thoughtful and reflective approach to scientific work, challenging existing paradigms and contributing to the future of the scientific process.

Implications of Pure Scientific Theories in Social Science

Pure scientific theory has enriched the theoretical rigour in social sciences, but it is still a challenge for its applicability and limitations. Critics such as Cilea and Tupan (2013), for example, object to the metaphorical transfer of the theory of relativity from Einstein's special and general principles designed to inform about relative-observer effects in physics into domains of social knowing, arguing that social entities are not like physical objects and thus cannot be interpreted simply according to the observer-relative norm. There is an offending question that applying relativistic understanding to social sciences would significantly reduce the complexities of human interactions by equating sociocultural differences with physical or biological phenomena. Similarly, the Heisenberg principle of uncertainty underscores how measurement in social investigation matters — but warns critics that it may lead to over-relativism as an excuse not just for naturalistic analysis and advocacy research in objective science, with all their elements contaminated by researchers' and participants' influence (Kashyap, 2014; Kusch, 2020; Smith, 2024).

Popper's demarcation criterion, falsification theory, and other critical method principles have significantly elevated the standards of proof within social sciences by prioritizing determinable hypotheses. While critics argue that strict adherence to falsifiability might exclude some complex social theories from proper science, the historical significance of Popper's emphasis on skepticism and experimentation as enduring influences in the discipline cannot be overstated. His work has reassured members of disciplines such as sociology to pursue empirical solidity, even in the face of complexity (Gutting, 1980). Popper's contribution seems historic and pivotal in making the emergence of post-positivism more scientific. It critiques deductive reasoning and disagrees with inductive reductionism.

Kuhn's concept of the paradigm shift has been instrumental in helping social scientists understand large-scale shifts from one dominant theoretical framework to another. Kuhn contributed to reclaiming the supremacy of science, though he postulated a relational and relative approach to scientific knowledge. Scientific knowledge rules the world as the dominant paradigm, and it holds hegemony until its anomalies are replaced by the revolution of the new knowledge system, i.e., paradigm II (e.g. shifting geocentrism into heliocentrism and shifting of Newtonian physics to modern quantum physics). All the paradigms (their crises and revolutions) are embedded in society's real contexts. For him, nothing is permanent, and the domination of scientific knowledge is also temporary, characterized as the 'paradigm shift'. Critics argue that Kuhn's model, which accommodated revolutionary change in natural sciences so well, may not be as accurate for social science as paradigms may coexist (Fuller, 2000).

Some critics suggest that Kuhn's idea of incommensurability may hinder interdisciplinary integration, as the social sciences thrive on diversity rather than paradigmatic hegemony (Matthews, 2024; Rorty, 2020). In conclusion, while scientific theories provide helpful jurisprudence, any abstraction into this specific use case may lead to the oversight of separate social science research problems, thereby emphasizing the need for a balanced approach to avoid dilemmas of pseudo-science and non-science.

Questioning on the Perfection of Science

Science, often revered as the highest pedestal of knowledge, has limitations. Whether science has been perfected or could ever be perfect has yet to be answered. With its observational, experimental, and replicable practices, science aims to provide logical explanations of how the natural world works. However, it is bound by human, methodological, and technological constraints. Even the most advanced instruments have their limits, unable to detect phenomena outside their capabilities, creating an apophatic zone in our understanding of reality. Moreover, science is not immune to bias, influenced by the cultural backgrounds of scientists, their funding sources, and the questions deemed valid based on prevailing paradigms (Kuhn, 1962). While science is a potent tool for uncovering the laws of nature, it is far from a sure path to absolute truth, but rather an iterative method that invites contemplation and intrigue, bound by human biases and material constraints.

While science is adept at pushing the boundaries of our understanding, it also encounters fundamentally unanswerable areas, particularly those that delve into metaphysics (e.g., the nature of existence before time and space), ethics, or subjective experiences. The realms of consciousness, moral philosophy, and existential meaning elude scientific analysis in the context of physicalism. These intersections prompt the question of what lies 'beyond' science. Some argue that for science to remain open, it must immerse itself in a more interdisciplinary context, integrating viewpoints from philosophy, art, and spirituality to offer holistic insights into the human experience (Feyerabend, 2010). This approach places scientific discoveries within a broader context, acknowledging that science informs us about the functioning of the world. However, a comprehensive understanding of purpose and value necessitates an integration of both humanistic and health sciences, stressing the need for a more interdisciplinary approach to science.

Risjord (2022) contends that the philosophy of science can offer valuable means for criticizing social science foundations and consequences by pushing them to question; breaking down fundamental beliefs about how things work requires more rigorous investigations. Similarly, Johansson (2016) argues that scientists can benefit from knowing philosophy because it fosters impartiality. This philosophical perspective helps scientists approach their work thoughtfully and unbiasedly when questioning methods and conclusions. Schurz (2013) argues that we need a unified approach integrating various scientific disciplines under a coherent philosophical framework for greater methodological and interpretative clarity.

Discussion

Philosophical inquiries and scientific innovations have been profoundly shaped by the zeal and passion of human beings in search of knowledge about everything they come across. This inquiry does arise in one of the most valued and criticized spheres of human knowledge – science, which shapes the world and advances people's lives. The methodologies used by science, while strong in their empirical approaches, also present biases and ethical issues. Understanding these distinctions is crucial to advancing the appreciation and analysis of scientific practice. We are living in a contested time-space continuum, a world characterized

by the digital divide, globalization, and new technological frontiers in information communication technology (ICT). This uneven access to scientific information exacerbates social and economic disadvantages. However, the potential of ICT and digital operational tools to bridge these gaps is immense, inspiring hope for a more equitable future. They provide quick access to scientific information and cooperation across geographical regions. While underserved and deprived communities may currently lack the appropriate enabling environment to engage, the future holds promise for narrowing the scientific and technological divide across the different societies and communities in the world.

This paper identifies a critical gap arising from serious epistemological incompatibilities between theories and methodologies within science practices. However, despite its methodological rigour, Positivism needed to produce an adequate structure and features of social reality. The predominance of the technique in scientific studies has led to the refinement of the method to such an acceptable degree that it has restricted the freedom of investigators in posing finer issues. Constructivism/ interpretivism is another research paradigm grounded on the subjectivist theory of knowledge, which asserts that knowledge is based on individual perspectives and experiences. However, it also presents some limitations, which debar its researchers from making generalizations and research bias. Nevertheless, both positivism and interpretivist cannot solve all the problems about realities. For example, some of the mysterious scientific problems and unsettled questions can be summarized below:

- Is this world knowable? How can we know that we know it? What is the validity of this knowing to be a 'science'?
- How can we begin to theorize the unfathomable origin of our universe? Is it even possible to comprehend? What is the nature of our reality, and how do we define what is 'real'?
- Is this world immortal or permanent? If yes, what is the driving force for this continuity? If not, what was before its formation or birth, and what will be after its disappearance or death?
- Are the laws of nature, these fundamental scientific principles, truly universal? Do they govern both the living and the inanimate, shaping the very fabric of our world?
- What is the philosophy of zero and infinity? Are they logical constructions that can be nullified or falsified?
- Why is the charge of a proton (p^+) and an electron (e^-) the same in magnitude, yet opposite in direction? ($+1e$ vs $-1e$, as of $+1.602 \times 10^{-19}$ Coulombs for the proton, -1.602×10^{-19} Coulombs for the electron)? What would our world look like if these charges were not in opposition?
- What is the mystery of other elementary particles, and what is the possibility and implication of anti-matter in this world?

The scientific method is defined with specific procedures, systematic approaches, tools, and techniques. However, methods are a relative construction in the context of our culture, society, and politics. Technical issues make ethical questions in social science even more sensitive and contextual. Recent encouragement of research commercialization and the drive to publish in prestigious journals threaten scientific research and practice with growing skepticism. Philosophical treatments of these concerns are enlightening, yet the constraints of methodologies restrain real-world applications. These areas needed more pluralism, flexibility, and ethical responsibility; everything currently needs to be added to the scientism-praising concept of post-philosophy. What is at stake is the change of prevailing institutional practices

and the redefinition of what counts as legitimate science. A more open and self-conscious approach to scientific business, empowered by critical thinking, allows the researcher to address contemporary research's ethical and methodical issues.

A critical lens must be focused on scientific practices in a more complex society seeking scientific solutions to global issues. Forcing criticism does not mean excluding scientific progress. It acts as a means of preventing applicable methodologies, more ethical standards, and future misuse of science and initiating a culture that promotes critical thinking that questions and fosters views that allow an all-round scrutiny of some of the presuppositions that undergird science. In this delicate balance, the main focus should be on creating an organizational culture that encourages criticism, where criticism is seen as a work of cooperation and not as confrontation. This not only helps create more critical thinking but also fosters more creativity due to intentionality to go against the grain and think about and work through solutions that are not conventional. In the long run, only the outcome of how humanity will be able to negotiate over the fine line between criticism and advancement of science to engender solutions favourable to the greater good of all people will define the direction of science.

The impact of funding and politics on scientific integrity has been a contested issue. Funding and, to a large extent, politics are profound and complex as they determine the research focus and direction and the analysis of results. It leads to the politicization of science because the public distrusts scientists and their claims because their work is being done along specific political affiliations that the public is unaware of. In the context of contemporary scientific research, the intersection of funding and political agendas poses a significant threat to scientific integrity. Indeed, these power politics are evident in scientific research and do not take a step away from intentional collaboration and the targeted mission of power elites and hegemony. For example, Rubinstein et al. (2018) consider such coupled dynamics of power and consensus within collaboration-cooperative environments, which indicate multi-layered interactions and the discomfort caused by hegemony in environments that influence collectivity. This discomfort underscores the need for change and reform. Similarly, Bano (2023) calls for challenging the dominant paradigms in the research, and it discusses the positive role of the decolonizing method in bringing change and presenting cultural superiority.

Conclusion

This review-based critique echoes the centrality of philosophy in the doing of science. Two research paradigms – positivism and constructivism can provide valuable approaches for any research and, at the same time, have their drawbacks when applied separately, which has been raised critically by post-positivists. Essentially, positivism neglects human subjectivity, hence reducing overall social phenomena to measurable parameters that can be empirically proven. On the other hand, the interpretive research paradigm can explain the meaning and context of human behaviour. However, it can be relativistic and may not possess scientific evidence data to build generalizable theories. The ethical issues arising from research commercialization and the institutionalization of research also explain why there is an urgent need for more self-reflecting scientific research that goes beyond the collection of facts and their analysis, stressing the importance of addressing ethical issues in research. Answering the difficulties arising from the interaction between science and societal factors, it is possible to define that only the critical approach can provide people with a better understanding of the results

obtained. All these criticisms have raised imperativeness for reflective and contextually sensitive frameworks in scientific inquiry.

All in all, the philosophy and practice of science still give an idea that they need to merge if the researchers are to address the advanced ethical, methodological, and epistemological issues of scientific research today. In particular, Einstein's theory of relativity, Heisenberg's principle of uncertainty, Popper's principle of falsification, and Kuhn's paradigm shift are the four ample assets contributed by pure science theorists to the broader spectrum of social science. Though this paper does not discuss much, Vendetta philosophy, Taoism, Marxism, Weberian perspective, political economics of science and technology, environmental politics, and sustainable development are some of the fundamental contributions of social science that a pure science domain should also read, embrace, and explore. For this, scientific research can be the bridging tool now becoming multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary. By encouraging a pluralistic and reflective culture of science, the researchers will be able to establish a more ethical and efficient paradigm of understanding reality. Introducing different perspectives in arguments is typically fruitful since one is forced to ask more questions and consider the epistemology of the specific science. In addition, by recognizing the interactive relationship between science and social factors, the researchers can understand how to deal with the problems and vices arising from funding constraints and politicization. Finally, the emphasis on philosophical contemplation in scientific work not only benefits the quality of the research but also reassures the audience about the value of their work, contributing to the development of science collectively improving the quality and dignity of human society and turning science into a nature-friendly asset for the global peace and harmony.

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